

CONTINUOUS PRODUCTION OF FIBRE REINFORCED THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES BY BRAIDING PULTRUSION

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ABSTRACT

The braiding pultrusion process is an innovative process chain to produce fibre reinforced thermoplastic profiles with a load adaptive fibre design. At first hybrid yarns are braided on a continuously fed mandrel. After the braiding process the hybrid textiles are heated, shaped and cooled down in a hot press unit. A pultrusion process for thermoplastic composites was designed and set up. The paper describes the project results and gives an outlook on future developments. A method is described how inserts can be integrated during the braiding process. The paper also describes a way to evaluate the economic factors of the process line. There are investigations to heat up the carbonfibre profiles with electrical resistance heating. First experimental results are listed.

The results show that an economical production is possible with the new technology. The presented concept for the insert integration was approved. During pull out tests the inserts could not be pulled out of the profiles. The maximum force was 6 kN.

1 INTRODUCTION

Thermoplastics have the advantage that they can be melted and consolidated. This leads to a short production time and to the possibility to recycle the parts. It is still a challenge to infiltrate the textile with thermoplastic matrices because of its high viscosity. [1], [5], [6]

This challenge can be solved by using a hybrid yarn. A hybrid yarn is a thermoplastic yarn combined with a reinforcing yarn (carbon or glass). The use of hybrid yarn brings the thermoplastic closer to the reinforcement filaments. [2] This gives more freedom in design and enables fast processes like the pultrusion process. A textile made from hybrid yarn can be handled and draped like a standard textile. Thus it is possible to orientate the fibre the way they are needed. [7], [8]

There are several technologies to produce a hybrid yarn (e.g. commingling or side by side winding). They have different effects on the composite. [3]

These hybrid yarns can be used in standard textile technologies like the braiding technology. In the ongoing project FLECHTTRUSION a hybrid yarn is produced by combining a carbon fibre and a polyamide fibre in a commingling process. The hybrid yarn is braided on a mandrel with integrated inserts and after this the braid is melted and consolidated in a rolling station. The aim of the project FLECHTTRUSION is to develop a continuous process chain for FRP. Figure 1 shows the steps of the process.

Figure 1: Flechttrusion process

A tool to evaluate the costs of the process chain is presented. The paper analyses a method to integrate inserts during the braiding step of the FLECHTTRUSION process. The results of the ongoing investigations in heating the profile by electrical resistance are presented.

2 ECONOMIC EVALUATION

To calculate the process costs a tool is designed in Excel. The main indicators are the line speed and the unit costs. The cycle time is related to the line speed. The line speed is restricted by the bottleneck of the process chain. It has been observed that braiding and consolidation are the speed-critical units of the FLECHTTRUSION. The tool can also be used for other applications.

The designed tool is based on the machine hour rate calculation [9]. To calculate the costs several information are needed. Information like material data and machine data can be loaded from a database of the tool. The whole calculation is divided into three steps.

The first step is the definition of general information about the part, which is to be analyzed. Necessary information is the dimensions of the part and the material combination, which can be selected from a database. In the first step also general information addicted to the company has to be tipped in. These are for example the loan costs of the shop floor workers, the costs for rent and the costs per kWh. [10]

In the second step the necessary process modules are selected from the database. If the required module is not listed, the database can be extended. In the database information about the energy consumption and the investment costs are stored. In the last step information about the number of shifts per day and the size of the batch size is asked. The result is the costs per part and the distribution of the costs on personal costs, machine costs and material costs is given.

A profile similar to an automotive bumper is selected. The length is set to 1.1 m and the capacity to 10,000 units per year. With a line speed of 0.1 m/min the part costs are 46 € per unit. The study also revealed that the proportion of legal costs (investment and labor) decreases exponentially with the increasing number of items (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Proportion of legal costs dependent on number of units

3 INTEGRATION OF INSERTS

At first the challenges and the concept is described. Then the experiment results will be presented. The inserts will be tested mechanically in the end.

3.1 Challenges and Concept

Inserts are needed to connect profiles with other parts. An insert could be integrated afterwards by drilling a hole into the profile. Drilling cuts the fibres what lowers the performance of the parts, because the flow of the forces threw the fibres is broken. The braiding technology has the advantage that the fibres can be laid around an insert during the braiding process. The insert has to be placed on the mandrel before the braiding process.

Figure 3: Mandrel with integrated insert before the braiding process

The integration of an insert in the braiding pultrusion process is a challenge. The insert should be secured for later torsion force. The insert has to be higher than the braid to get braided inside, but lower than the profile to not disturb the consolidation process. Another problem is corrosion between the composite and the metallic insert. Figure 4 illustrates the problem with the height of the insert.

Figure 4: Challenge of the insert integration

The problem is solved with a braiding assistance. The assistance guides the hybrid yarns during the overbraiding process. The assistance is chopped before the consolidation process. The insert itself is made out of stainless steel to avoid corrosion.

3.2 Demonstrator Production

The mandrel is prepared for the inserts, which are placed in it. For the mandrel glass foam is chosen, which is overbraided by a radial braiding machine with four layers of Twintex®. The braiding process worked fully automated without interruption by the inserts. After the pressing process little rework was necessary.

Figure 5: Steps of the demonstrator production

3.3 Optical and Mechanical Evaluation

The demonstrators are checked optically for defects, which might occur during the shaping process. The cross sections are embedded in epoxy resin and polished. A low number of defects is detected within the cross sections. There are no unmelted thermoplastic fibres. When the thermoplastic fibres don't melt completely they can be detected, because their diameter is larger than the diameter of the glass fibres. The cross sections are shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Cross Section of the profile

The inserts are tested according to ASTM D7332/D7332M – 09. The test is adapted to the profile geometry, because the ASTM standard doesn't suit for a profile piece. The test set up for the pull out test is shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Pull-Out Test

The result of the test is that the inserts can't be pulled out of the profile. The experiment was repeated four times with each foam core. The result is presented in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Average result of the Pull Out Tests

The rise of the force is nearly constant until the maximum force of 6.5 kN in average for the glass foam and 7 kN for the aluminum foam. The standard deviation was 522 N for the glass foam and 206 N for the aluminum foam. The profiles fail and break without pulling out the insert. The graph shows a mixture of a brittle and a ductile material. The brittle behavior comes from the cracking of the fibres and the ductile behavior from the removal between mandrel and the material. The tests were performed with 4 Layers of glass fibre and polypropylene braid and two different types of mandrels: aluminium and glass.

4 HEATING PROFILES WITH ELECTRICAL RESISTANCE

Since carbon fibres are electroconductive they can be heated up by electricity. For that, we have developed an experimental setup to heat profiles composed of carbon and polyamide fibres. The carbon fibres are contacted by metallic clamps and the current between these contacts heats up the whole profile very fast. The new principle is illustrated in Figure 9. The advantage of the new technology is that several layers can be heated up simultaneously. With other techniques just the top layer is heated and the other layers have to be heated by convection through the layers. Therefore,

electrical resistance heating enables a fast and effective heating of carbon fibre reinforced profiles.

Figure 9: Concept for the modification

In ongoing experiments the heating behavior of braided parts made out of commingled carbon fibres and polyamide fibres is evaluated. The experimental setup, as shown in Figure 10, simulates the consolidation cylinders of the production process. The heating time in the experiment corresponds to the feed rate in the future production process, which means that we can reach the consolidation temperature in the same time a specific area of the endless profile needs from one cylinder to the other.

The current is generated by an induction device from IFF. The frequency can be preselected between 8 kHz and 30 kHz with an amperage up to 80 A. The transformer provides galvanic separation and transformation to safety-low-voltage (below 50 V).

Figure 10: Experimental setup

The quality of the heating and the consolidation process is determined by parameters like amperage and frequency of the electrical power on the one hand and textile properties on the other hand. The aim of the project is to heat up the profile as smooth as possible without burning it to achieve optimum conditions for the in-line consolidation of the parts.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The FLECHTTRUSION is a braiding pultrusion process, which can produce continuously fibre reinforced thermoplastic profiles. In the process a commingled hybrid yarn is braided around a mandrel and consolidated in a rolling station.

In this paper the product requirements for a bumper profile are identified and several possible processes were combined by network diagrams. The production costs for 10.000 units per year were

roughly calculated to 46 € per unit.

The braiding technology has the potential to integrate inserts during the process. The challenge to integrate inserts in the braiding pultrusion is quite high because the requirements are different. In this paper a method is presented which meets both requirements.

The development of the FLECHTRUSION is not finished and there is potential for a high economic process for high performance profiles. The use of carbon fibres gives the possibility to use the resistance heating technology, which is high efficient and very fast. There are still experiments running.

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Figure 11: Emblem of the Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Energy

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